

**Modeling and Characterization of
Multidirectionally Reinforced Ceramic Matrix Composites**
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1. ABSTRACT

Two research efforts have been underway to (a) fabricate three dimensionally (3-D) reinforced fabric ceramic matrix composites (CMC s), and (b) to model the elastic behavior of fabric CMCs. These efforts are part of a research program for the processing-characterization-properties studies of fabric ceramic matrix composites. 3-D woven and braided fiber preforms are infiltrated with glass and glass-ceramic matrices through a multiple sol-gel infiltration process. The solids content of the sol is varied to optimize the composite density which ranges within 85-90% of theoretical density. The modeling effort is currently limited to 2-D woven CMCs. The elastic stiffness of woven fabric composites has been analyzed using a fiber bundle model in which undulations in the longitudinal and transverse fibers have been taken into account. The effect of fabrication-induced voids in the intertow spaces has also been considered and found to play an important role in the composite stiffness.

KEYWORDS: WOVEN CMC, STIFFNESS, SOL-GEL PROCESSING, 3-D CMCs

2. INTRODUCTION

Fabric composites are gaining increasing popularity in the fabrication of structural components. The use of woven fabrics, rather than non-woven unidirectional plies, for making composites offers advantages such as relative ease of handling in fabrication, more balanced mechanical behavior in the fabric plane and better drapeability, which allows the material to conform to complex shapes[1].

Fabric CMCs have been formed through a variety of processes including chemical vapor infiltration (CVI), polymer pyrolysis, and sol-gel techniques. The mechanical properties of ceramic matrix composites are influenced by the fiber architecture and the overall porosity and porosity distribution within the matrix. It is, therefore, a processing objective of this study to achieve uniformity and continuity of matrix distribution in a 3-D composite both in the interbundle and intrabundle pores of the preform during the green

structure development and to maintain and improve this homogeneity on high temperature consolidation. The analytical study presented here also addresses the influence of the undulations in the woven fiber bundles and of the matrix porosity on the mechanical behaviour of the composite. A 2-D composite system was chosen for this part of the study.

The sol-gel infiltration technique involves the use of a ceramic sol - consisting of fine, 10-20nm size ceramic particles in a solvent, to infiltrate the preform. The sol acts as a carrier, binder and filler and, on drying, can be sintered to form the ceramic or glass matrix. This technique has the advantage of being able to infiltrate relatively dense preforms due to the fine particle size of the ceramic in the sol. The viscosity and solids fraction of the infiltrate can be varied by changing the dilution of the solvent or by adding colloidal particles to it to obtain optimum infiltration conditions. Also, multicomponent sols can be mixed at a submicron scale to form uniform and novel microstructures on high temperature consolidation.

One such study has been done by Marple and Green [3,4] on 62% dense, presintered alumina powder preforms which were infiltrated with a silica precursor and then crystallized to form mullite grains around the alumina particles. Our study is different in approach from that of Marple and Green in that the objective here is to use dense 3-D fiber preforms to obtain fiber reinforced ceramic matrix composites. The resin transfer molding technique is used to infiltrate the ceramic matrix precursors in the preform.

In spite of their potential applications, the understanding of the mechanical behavior of woven composites is still very limited. Ishikawa and Chou introduced fiber undulation model and bridging model to 2-dimensional biaxial plain and satin fabric composites and made comparisons with mosaic model [5,6]. Yang and Chou adopted the concept of fiber crimping to represent triaxial woven fabric composites [7]. In the mosaic model, a fabric composite is simplified as an assemblage of pieces of cross-ply laminates. The fiber undulation model takes into account the continuity of fiber yarns. In the bridging model, fabrics are assumed to be comprised of a number of laminate pieces including interlaced and uninterlaced regions to represent satin fabrics. In both models, fiber undulation is considered only in the loading direction. These two models allow bending to occur, which is especially suitable for studying a one-ply fabric composite. For composite laminates composed of multi-layer fabrics, the effect of extension-bending coupling, which is due to nonsymmetry of the $[0/90]$ fabrics, is diminished rapidly as the number of layers increases. Kuo and Chou recently introduced a fiber bundle model to study the mechanical behavior of a plain weave SiC/SiC fabric ceramic composite, in which the laminate is comprised of multi-layer fabrics[8,9]. In this paper, the fabrication-induced voids in intertow space are studied. Since fiber undulation in both directions has been considered, the unit cell adopted herein can best describe the geometrical configurations.

3. SOL-GEL PROCESSING OF FABRIC CMCs

Figure 1 shows a schematic of the process used. Two kinds of preforms were used: (i) braided Nextel (alumino-silicate fiber) preforms of 60-70% fiber volume fraction and (ii) 3-dimensional orthogonal woven Tyranno fiber preforms of 47% fiber volume fraction. The matrices deposited were: a glassy silica matrix and, for better refractory properties, a glass-ceramic alumino-silicate matrix. Both types of sols were prepared using organo-metallic precursors and standard recipes in the literature [10,11]. The matrix, in the form of a ceramic sol, was infiltrated in the preform under suction and pressure. Multiple infiltrations were used to obtain green densities over 85%. The composites were hot pressed at pressures of 1000-2000psi and temperatures of 1100-1500° C. Final composite densities were measured using the Archimedes principle.

Figure 2 shows the green structure development in the preform with each infiltration. The relative densities were estimated from the weight gain in the composite after each infiltration. The upper curve is for the braided Nextel preform composite and the lower one for the woven Tyranno preform composite. The infiltrate for the first two infiltrations of the Nextel preform was a silical sol mixed with 0.5 μm diameter colloidal silica particles with an overall solids fraction of 30 wt %. The next three infiltrations were done with a silica sol (of 7wt% solids fraction and particle size of 20-50nm) without colloidal particles. The same infiltration procedure was followed for the Tyranno preform except that the silica sol and particles are replaced by an alumino-silicate sol and particles of size 1-2 μm .

In both cases, the curves tend to saturate after five infiltrations. This is probably so because of the closure of surface porosity of the preform so that no further weight gain can occur. This observation also led to the optimal infiltration procedure where the high solids fraction infiltrate is used in the first two infiltrations when the preform porosity is high and accessible and is followed by the use of the dilute sol (with the fine particle size) for the subsequent infiltrations to fill up the fine residual porosity homogeneously in the preform. Figure 3 shows the green microstructure of the Nextel braid after five infiltrations as described. The matrix with the 0.5 μm colloidal silica particles is seen to be homogeneously distributed between the fibers.

The green density of the Nextel preform was seen to be higher than that of the Tyranno preform. We feel that this is due to the different fiber architecture in the two preforms. Although the braided Nextel preform has a higher fiber volume fraction, its porosity is more accessible to the infiltrate since a high percentage (47 volume %) of fibers lie uniaxially along one direction. In the 3-D woven Tyranno preform on the other hand, there are 8.5 volume % fibers in the z-direction and the rest of the 47% are distributed uniformly in the x- and y- directions. Such a fiber architecture would provide more obstacles to the infiltrate flow. It is important to remember however, that the 3-D

orthogonal fiber architecture of the Tyranno preform would provide better isotropic strength in the final composite.

Analogous to the constraints offered by the preform architecture to the flow of the infiltrate into the spaces within the preform, it is found that the rigid preform offers constraints to the sintering of the matrix at high temperatures to form a uniform microstructure. High temperature consolidation of the Tyranno fiber/ alumino-silicate matrix composites was carried out by hot pressing at pressures of 1000-2000 psi and temperatures of 1100-1500° C. It was found that addition of borosilicate glass powder to the matrix was necessary as a sintering aid to obtain a uniformly dense microstructure. Relative densities of 85-90 % theoretical and room temperature flexure strengths of 100MPa were measured for the composites. Figure 4 shows the microstructure of a Tyranno fiber / alumino-silicate matrix composite hot pressed at 1000psi and 1500°C.

4. MODELING OF THE ELASTIC PROPERTIES OF FABRIC CMCs

4.1 GEOMETRICAL RELATIONS

Woven fabrics are formed by interlacing two sets of mutually orthogonal yarns: the warp and fill (or weft) yarns. The geometric pattern of bi-axial woven fabrics is shown in Figure 5. The bundle width and thickness are denoted as 'a' and 'h', respectively. The gap between two neighboring bundles is denoted as 'b'. The fiber undulations are identical in the x and y directions. The space not occupied by fiber bundles is called intertow space in this paper.

The cross-section of fiber bundles is assumed as elliptical with major axis 'a' and minor axis 'h' as shown in Figure5. The geometry of a fiber bundle can be described by defining its center line. The slope of the undulating fiber can be obtained directly from the center line, and the angle between the longitudinal yarn and the x-axis is

$$\theta_x = \pm \tan^{-1} \left[\phi \sin \frac{x}{a+b} \pi \right] \quad (1)$$

where $\phi (= \frac{\pi}{2} \frac{h}{a+b})$ is a constant reflecting the fiber waviness. Equation (1) indicates that the slopes of two neighboring longitudinal yarns are just opposite in sign but have the same value.

4.2 BUNDLE PROPERTIES

The linear constitutive relations for the constituents of the composite can be written as

$$\sigma_i^k = Q_{ij}^k \varepsilon_j \quad (2)$$

where k represents L , T or m , which stand for longitudinal yarn (LY), transverse yarn (TY) and the intertow matrix, respectively; i and j represent x or y . The stiffness constants can be related to the reduced stiffnesses with respect to the principal material coordinate of fiber bundles. The Q_{ij}^k 's are given by [7,8].

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{xx}^L &= Q_{11} \cos^4\theta_x + 2(Q_{12} + 2Q_{66})\cos^2\theta_x \sin^2\theta_x + Q_{22}\sin^4\theta_x \\ Q_{xy}^L &= Q_{12} \cos^2\theta_x + Q_{23}\sin^2\theta_x \\ Q_{yy}^L &= Q_{22} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The 1-direction in Eq.(3) refers to the longitudinal direction, and 2 and 3 refer to the transverse directions. The fiber bundle is assumed as transversely isotropic.

4.3 ISO-PHASE MODE(IPM) AND RANDOM-PHASE MODE(RPM)

Single-layer[4,5] and multi-layer[7,8] fabric composites differ in that the former allows bending to occur due to the nonsymmetry of the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ fiber arrangement. In the multi-layer analysis, the extension-bending coupling effect is inversely proportional to the number of layers, and the displacement compatibility at the laminate interface needs to be maintained. A factor, however, to be considered in multi-layer analysis is the fabric stacking sequences. Two limiting cases are discussed in this paper.

The first limiting case is the perfect stacking where the relative positions of all the layers are the same as shown in Figure 6a. It is assumed that any section normal to the load direction remains so after deformation to ensure displacement compatibility. Therefore, the strains are assumed as $\varepsilon_x \equiv \varepsilon_x(x)$ and $\varepsilon_y \equiv \varepsilon_y(y)$.

The stresses in the composite depend on the biaxial loading conditions. To simplify the problem, the Poisson's effect caused by transverse loads is averaged as the following form:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_x^L \\ \sigma_x^T \\ \sigma_x^m \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} Q_{xx}^L & Q_{xy}^L \\ Q_{xx}^T & Q_{xy}^T \\ Q_{xx}^m & Q_{xx}^m \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_x(x) \\ \varepsilon_2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Here, ε_2 is the average value of $\varepsilon_y(y)$ over the unit cell. The force (per layer) acting on the cross-section at x can be obtained as

$$F_1 = A_L \sigma_x^L + A_T \sigma_x^T + A_m \sigma_x^m \quad (5)$$

The A_L , A_T and A_m are cross-sectional areas of LY, TY and intertow matrix, respectively. In the range $0 \leq x \leq (a+b)/2$, $0 \leq y \leq (a+b)/2$, $-h \leq z \leq h$, they can be approximated as following

$$\begin{aligned} A_L &= \frac{\pi}{8} ha \frac{1}{\cos \theta_x} \\ A_T &= \frac{1}{2} h(a+b) \left[1 - \left(\frac{2x}{a} \right)^2 \right]^{1/2} \left(1 + \frac{1}{4} \phi^2 \right) & 0 \leq x \leq a/2 \\ A_T &= 0 & a/2 \leq x \leq (a+b)/2 \\ A_m &= \eta [h(a+b) - A_L - A_T] \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where $0 \leq \eta \leq 1$ reflects the matrix content in the intertow space; $\eta=0$ means the space is empty, while $\eta=1$ indicates the space is completely filled. F_1 of Eq.(5) is a constant to ensure force equilibrium. Substituting Eq.(4) into Eq.(5) and taking average of $\epsilon_x(x)$ over the unit cell, we obtain the following relation

$$E_c = \frac{1 - C_2^2}{h(a+b)C_1} \quad (7)$$

where the constants are

$$(C_1, C_2) = \frac{2}{(a+b)} \int_0^{(a+b)/2} [Q_{xx}^k A_L + Q_{22}^k A_T + Q_{11}^m A_m]^{-1} (1, Q_{xy}^k A_L + Q_{xy}^k A_T + Q_{12}^m A_m) dx \quad (8)$$

The evaluations of C_1 and C_2 and thus E_c can be carried out through numerical integrations of Eq.(8).

Another limiting case of fabric arrangement in a laminate is the random-phase mode (RPM) shown in Figure 6b where the number of layers is infinite and the stacking is completely random. Under such assumptions, the average stiffnesses and hence the deformations of all sections are the same. The composite strains are assumed as $\epsilon_x(x, y, z) \equiv \epsilon_1$ and $\epsilon_y(x, y, z) \equiv \epsilon_2$.

The procedures for evaluating the forces in the layers are the same as in IPM. It should be noted that unlike the IPM where the force on each layer is the same, the force in this case is a function of x , and this function is different from layer to layer. However, the total force on each cross-section of the whole composite laminate remains constant. Based on the assumption of random layer distribution, the average value of the force per layer can be obtained by the integration of the stress over the thickness direction, and this value should be equal to the one obtained by averaging the force in the x -direction.

$$\bar{F}_1 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N F_1^i(x) = \frac{2}{a+b} \int_0^{(a+b)/2} F_1(x) dx \quad (9)$$

where $F_1^i(x)$ is the force on the i -th layer, and N is the total number of layers. The integration gives the following result.

$$E_c = \frac{D_1}{h(a+b)} \left(1 - \left(\frac{D_1}{D_2} \right)^2 \right) \quad (10)$$

where the coefficients are

$$\begin{aligned} D_1 &= \frac{\pi h a}{8} \left[Q_{11} \left(1 - \frac{3}{4} \phi^2 \right) + (Q_{12} + 2Q_{66}) \phi^2 + Q_{22} \left(1 + \frac{1}{4} \phi^2 \right) \right] \\ &\quad + \eta Q_{11}^m h \left[a+b - \frac{\pi}{4} a \left(1 + \frac{1}{4} \phi^2 \right) \right] \\ D_2 &= \frac{\pi h a}{8} \left[2 Q_{12} + \frac{1}{2} \phi^2 Q_{23} \right] + \eta Q_{12}^m h \left[a+b - \frac{\pi}{4} a \left(1 + \frac{1}{4} \phi^2 \right) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

4.4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The elastic behavior of SiC/SiC plain weave composites fabricated by the chemical vapor infiltration (CVI) method is discussed. The material properties used for estimating fiber bundle properties are: Young's modulus of Nicalon fiber=200 GPa, Young's modulus of SiC matrix = 400 GPa [7,8]. The bundle properties are $E_1=314$ GPa and $E_2=280$ GPa. The effect of fiber undulation on composite Young's modulus is shown in figure 7. The corresponding results predicted by mosaic model [4,5] are also indicated. Both IPM and RPM give very reasonable correlation with experimental results. Two factors are responsible for the slightly increasing values of composite stiffness with increasing h/a ratio. The first one is that E_1 and E_2 are very close for the fiber bundle, so the reduction in stiffness due to fiber undulation is small. The second factor is that the bundle volume in the unit cell increases with fiber undulation, and therefore the overall stiffness is enhanced. Figure 8 shows the effect of SiC intertow matrix on the composite stiffness for $h/a=0.11$. The results indicate that the matrix content is a significant factor in affecting the composite stiffness due to the fact that SiC matrix has relatively high Young's modulus compared to that of the fiber bundle.

5. CONCLUSIONS

A sol-gel infiltration technique was developed for the formation of ceramic matrix composites with 3-D fiber preforms. The infiltration conditions were optimized with respect to solids fraction of the infiltrate for successive infiltrations and preform architecture to achieve high green densities (upto 90%) and homogeneous filling of preform. High temperature consolidation of these composites was done by hot pressing and the final

densities and flexure strengths measured. Relative densities of 85-90 % theoretical and room temperature flexure strengths of 100MPa were achieved for the composites.

The elastic properties of 2-D woven fabric CMCs have also been modeled. The theoretical analysis shows that the stiffnesses predicted by IPM and RPM are fairly close. Closed form solutions have been obtained for the composite stiffness in the RPM case. The effects of the matrix content in the intertow space and the fiber waviness on the composite stiffness have been studied. It has been shown that the contribution of the intertow matrix is an important factor, because the modulus of SiC matrix is relatively high. It is also found that as the fiber waviness increases, the composite stiffness increases slightly. Theoretical results by the present model have been compared with the experiment data, and it is shown that both IPM and RPM give better predictions than the mosaic model.

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Figure 1. Schematic of the infiltration and consolidation process.

Figure 2. Step-wise study of the green density of the preform with each infiltration.

Figure 3. SEM micrograph of a Nextel fiber preform infiltrated with a silica matrix showing the green structure of the matrix with colloidal silica particles.

Figure 4. SEM micrograph of a Tyranno fiber preform infiltrated with an aluminosilicate matrix and hot-pressed at 1500°C.

Figure 5. Unit cell for a plain weave fabric

(a) Iso-Phase Mode

(b) Random-Phase Mode

Figure 6. Fabric stacking geometry

Figure 7. Effect of the fiber waviness on the composite stiffness

• : Experimental data for the SiC/SiC composite [8,9]

Figure 8. Effect of the matrix content in the intertow space on SiC/SiC stiffness

• : Experimental data for the SiC/SiC composite [8,9]

